

Metal Complexes of 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-Methyl Triazene N-oxide

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Isolation and properties of a number of metal complexes of 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide have been described. Based on magnetic moments, electronic spectra, infra-red spectral studies and thermogravimetric analysis, the structures of these compounds have been discussed.

CO-ordination ability of different bidentate triazene N-oxides and their analytical applications have been studied extensively¹⁻⁶. Tridentate triazene N-oxides with a carboxyl group have been introduced very recently as an excellent group of analytical reagents⁷⁻¹¹. Such a reagent as 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide was found to be quite specific for the direct gravimetric determination of titanium even in presence of niobium and tantalum¹¹, though it reacts with a number of metal ions. Niobium and tantalum were kept in solution by the use of tartaric acid.

In this paper is reported the method of isolation, the properties and the structures of the various metal compounds formed by this triazene N-oxide. In Table I is listed their physical properties and elementary analytical data.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus: Preparation of 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide has already been described¹¹.

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer was used for the measurements of absorbances. Conductance experiments were made with a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Magnetic measurements were done in a Gouy balance which was calibrated with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate (II). The IR spectra in the solid state were taken in KBr disc with the help of Perkin Elmer 137 IR spectrophotometer. Chevenard-Joumier thermobalance, ADAMEL type CTTB No 107 was used to record photographically the change in weight of the substance as a function of temperature. The rate of heating was 5°C per minute.

TABLE—1

Complex	Colour	μ_{eff} in B. M.	Elemental Analysis*			
			Found		Calc.	
			%Metal	%N	%Metal	%N
Ni(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)H ₂ O	Yellow	3.23	21.71	15.24	21.74	15.56
Ni(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)H ₂ O	Grey	3.04	21.70	14.86	21.74	15.56
Co(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)H ₂ O	Reddish brown	4.43	22.08	14.32	21.81	15.55
Cu(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)	Green	1.89	23.40	15.94	24.76	16.37
Ni(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)Py ₂ H ₂ O	Bluish Green	3.17	13.74	16.40	13.71	16.36
prepared from the grey variety.						
Ni(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)Py ₂ H ₂ O	Green	3.21	14.68	15.24		
prepared from the yellow variety.						
H[Fe(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃) ₂]	Apparently black	5.91	has already been reported in our earlier work ¹²			
NH ₄ [Fe(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃) ₂]	Violet	6.02				
VO(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)	Green	1.67				
H[VO(OH) ₂ (C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)]	Yellow	Diamagnetic				
V ₂ O ₄ (C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃) ₂	Brown	0.96				
Pd(C ₈ H ₇ O ₃ N ₃)H ₂ O	Yellowish brown	Diamagnetic	32.52	13.06	33.50	13.23
Pd(C ₈ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃) ₂	Brown	„	21.35	16.20	21.59	17.05

* Since the complexes explode violently at their decomposition temperatures, analysis of C and H were not attempted and moreover, due to this nitrogen analysis was not consistent always.

Preparation of the complexes: Aquo [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] nickel (II). 1(a) The hot solutions of 1 g of the ligand in 50 ml of ethanol and 1.2 g of nickel (II) chloride hexahydrate in 30 ml of ethanol were mixed together. 8 ml of 1M sodium hydroxide solution were added and then the mixture was digested on a boiling water bath for about an hour when a yellow precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in air. λ_{\max} in pyridine are at 17.5-17.8 (37.7), 12.8 (sh), 11.9 (16.4) kK (ϵ_{\max} are given in parentheses). It is almost insoluble in methanol, chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene but highly soluble in hot pyridine.

1(b) Nickel complex of the ligand was also prepared similarly but in ice-cold condition when a grey white product was formed. This was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried in air. λ_{\max} : 17.5-17.8 (35.1), 12.8(sh), 11.9 (15.1) kK in pyridine solution. It is almost insoluble in methanol, chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene but highly soluble in pyridine at room temperature.

Aquo dipyridine [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] nickel (II).

2(a) About 1g of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$ prepared in hot condition (method 1a) was dissolved in pyridine (15 ml) by digesting on a boiling water bath. This was then diluted with water to about 75 ml and kept overnight. The crystals separated were filtered, washed with water and dried in air. The compound is unstable and slowly loses pyridine at room temperature.

2(b) About 1g of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$ obtained in the cold (method 1b) was treated as described above. The compound is stable at room temperature.

3. Aquo [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] cobalt (II). For the preparation of this compound, the same procedure as suggested for the isolation of nickel (II) complex in method 1a from hot ethanolic medium was followed using 1.2g of cobalt chloride hexahydrate. It is almost insoluble in methanol, benzene, chloroform and carbontetrachloride.

4. [3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] copper (II). The complex was prepared by adding an ethanolic solution of 0.8g of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to a hot solution of 1 g of the triazene N-oxide also in ethanol (25 ml). The complex precipitated instantaneously. This was digested for a few minutes. The green crystalline complex was filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in air. λ_{\max} in pyridine solution is at 15.4-15.6 kK with an extinction value of 89.

It is almost insoluble in methanol, benzene, chloroform, carbontetrachloride and acetone. It is slightly soluble in nitrobenzene but has appreciable solubility in hot pyridine.

About 1 g of the above copper(II) complex was dissolved in 20 ml of pyridine by heating. It was then diluted with water and kept as such for a few hours. The compound that separated was filtered, washed with water and dried in air.

The infra-red spectra of this compound is identical with the parent compound without pyridine.

5. Aquo[3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] palladium (II).

0.85g of palladium chloride were dissolved in 30 ml of water containing about 1g of potassium chloride by boiling. To this solution, an ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the reagent (1g) was added followed by a few drops of 2N hydrochloric acid solution. The yellowish brown precipitate appeared on digestion on a water bath was filtered, washed with hot water and dried in air. It is slightly soluble in ethanol, benzene, chloroform and carbontetrachloride.

6. Bis-[3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene N-oxide] palladium (II).

A solution of lithium tetrachloropalladate (II) was prepared in acetone (30 ml) using 0.85g of palladium chloride and 1g of lithium chloride. To this, 2g of the ligand solution in 25 ml of acetone was added followed by 8 ml of 1N sodium hydroxide solution. The solution with the precipitate was kept overnight and then filtered, washed with ice-cold acetone and dried in air. The compound is slightly soluble in acetone, methanol, chloroform and pyridine.

Preparations of iron (III), vanadium (IV and V) complexes have already been described^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic moments of the nickel (II) and cobalt (II) compounds and their insolubility in all organic solvents, except in highly co-ordinating pyridine, suggest that they may have polymeric octahedral structure. The two nickel (II) compounds are definitely polymorphous. The greyish white form, which is more soluble in pyridine than the yellow one, on prolong boiling in ethanol changes to yellow variety. In pyridine solutions, however, they have identical spectra, characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry. On the isolation of the complexes from the pyridine solutions, it is observed that the resultant compound which is obtained from the yellow variety is much more unstable than that obtained from the grey variety. The former loses pyridine continuously at room temperature whereas from the latter, pyridine is lost only when it is heated.

The thermogravimetric curves of these two compounds are shown in Fig.1. From curve A, it appears that the dipyridine complex obtained from the grey compound loses weight at 110° with an unstable intermediate which decomposes further at 133° and finally above 170° it gives a stable product. The first weight loss between 110° and 133° corresponds to the combined loss of one pyridine molecule and a water molecule whereas the last pyridine molecule is lost in the next step with the ultimate formation of an apparently tri-coordinated nickel (II) compound having the composition $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)$. But the other compound (curve B) from which smell of pyridine is perceptible even at room temperature, loses weight appreciably from 68° and above 82°, the loss in weight corresponds to the escape of a molecule of pyridine and a molecule of water. Thus on

reaction with pyridine, both the polymeric compounds change to the monomeric forms having the composition $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{Py}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and probably they exist in two isomeric forms and so have different thermal stability.

Fig. 1. Thermogravimetric curves :
 Curve A : $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{Py}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ obtained from the grey form.
 Curve B : $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{Py}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ prepared from the yellow variety.
 Curve C : $\text{H}[\text{VO}(\text{OH})_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)]$

The apparently tri-coordinated copper (II) complex is almost insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, benzene, carbontetrachloride, acetonitrile but soluble in dimethylformamide and pyridine. Because of their insolubility in non-coordinating solvents their cryoscopic or ebullioscopic measurements could not be made. When the original compound is crystallized from a solution in pyridine, the latter is not observed to coordinate.

A number of apparently tri-coordinated copper (II) compounds are known which are actually dimeric, with square planar configuration¹³. So the isolated copper complex can be expected to have similar dimeric structure. There may be two dimeric forms in which either the N-oxide oxygen¹⁴ or the carboxyl oxygen¹⁵ acting as a bridging atom. However, if the N-oxide oxygen is the bridging atom, the two copper atoms will be very proximate and as such will have subnormal magnetic moment. In this connection, it may be stated that with some Schiff base complexes of copper (II), formed of 5-substituted salicylaldehyde and anthranilic acid, which has some similarity with the triazene N-oxide, direct spin-spin interaction or super-exchange type of interaction is not possible between the two copper ions due to the non-planarity of the eight membered ring formed by bridging through the carboxyl oxygen¹⁵. Since $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)$ has a magnetic moment of 1.89 B.M., it may be stated to have the latter type of structure.

Palladium (II) forms both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes, having the compositions $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)_2$ respectively; these two complexes being square planar, the ligand can be said to act differently, either as tridentate or as bidentate depending on the reaction condition.

The paramagnetic (μ_{eff} 1.67 B.M.) $\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)$ complex is apparently four-coordinated. It may as well be suggested to have a higher coordination number

by bridging through oxygen (N-oxide or carboxylic or both) of the chelating agent because of its insolubility in most of the organic solvents.

Vanadium (V) forms two different complexes, one yellow at pH 5 and the other brown at pH 1, with only one ligand per metal ion. The brown complex is slightly paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=0.96$ B.M.) whereas the other is fully diamagnetic. The yellow compound is soluble in highly polar solvents such as water, methanol, ethanol, pyridine but insoluble in benzene, chloroform and carbontetrachloride. From the aqueous solution, it is absorbed completely by an anion exchanger and behaves as an 1:1 electrolyte in methanol ($\Lambda_{\infty}=102$) and hence has been formulated as $\text{H}[\text{VO}(\text{OH})_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)]$. Thermogravimetric analysis (cf. Fig. 1 curve) shows that at 160° it loses a molecule of water.

The brown compound in pure methanol is a non-electrolyte though in water-methanol mixture (1:1) it behaves as an uni-univalent electrolyte ($\Lambda_{\infty}=98$ with $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution). It seems that the yellow complex on acidification and boiling dimerizes first which then by protonation sets the carboxyl acid group free.

The Infra-red Spectra : The IR spectrum of the free ligand confirms its N-oxide structure and as such a sharp N-H stretch is observed at 3176 cm^{-1} . The O-H stretching frequency of the carboxyl group appears as a broad band centered at 2940 cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric stretch occurs at 1680 cm^{-1} whereas the corresponding symmetric stretch is at 1230 cm^{-1} .

On complexation, the N-H band disappears and the asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl group is also lowered except in the brown vanadium (V) complex. In most of the compounds, the correct assignment of the asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl group is not possible since on complexation, it is so lowered that it appears along with the other bands.

The presence of water in the 1:1 complexes of the cobalt(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) is confirmed from their spectra. The IR spectrum of copper (II) complex, on the other hand, shows the absence of water band establishing that it has the apparently tri-coordinated structure.

In $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_3)_2$ the carboxyl groups are bonded since the asymmetric stretch appears at 1604 cm^{-1} . Moreover, with the N-H band absent and the O-H stretch appearing at 3448 cm^{-1} the reagent appears to have N-hydroxy form and this is the only case known where the ligand exists in that form only.

In the yellow vanadium (V) complex, the asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl group appears at 1616 cm^{-1} whereas that in the brown vanadium (V) compound is found at 1686 cm^{-1} proving the existence of the free carboxylic acid groups. The two hydroxyl groups are probably occupying the *cis* positions in the former complex and since two different co-ordinating atoms (nitrogen and oxygen of the N-oxide group) are present opposite to those groups, the OH stretch appears, therefore, as a doublet at 3078 and 3000 cm^{-1} . The bonded carboxyl group in the yellow compound must be *trans* to the vanadyl oxygen and as such the V=O stretch

appears in the lower energy region (925 cm^{-1}), but with the carboxyl group free in the brown variety, the $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretch appears at 995 cm^{-1} .

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